

Synthesis and Biocidal Activity of some 1,3,4-Oxadiazolo[3,2-*a*]-*s*-triazine-5,7-diones

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Our interest in the chemistry of some substituted-oxadiazoles and *s*-substituted-triazines with multifarious biological activity has promoted us to synthesise 1,3,4-oxadiazolo[3,2-*a*]-*s*-triazine-5,7-diones and evaluate their biological activity.

The title compounds were synthesised by the condensation of oxadiazolylureas with ethyl chloroformate. Oxadiazolylureas were obtained by reacting 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles with ethyl chloroformate followed by treatment with 4-chloroaniline. 2-Amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles were prepared by the oxidative cyclisation of the aldehyde semicarbazones by the reported method¹. Structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their analytical and ir and ¹H nmr spectral data.

	R'	R''	R'''		R'	R''	R'''
4a	Me	Me	Et	4g	Me	Et	Pr
b	Et	Et	Et	h	Et	Me	Pr
c	Me	Et	Et	i	Me	Me	Bu
d	Ft	Me	Et	j	Ft	Et	Bu
e	Me	Me	Pr	k	Me	Et	Bu
f	Et	Et	Pr	l	Et	Me	Bu

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) $\text{ClCO}_2\text{Et}/\text{Et}_3\text{N}/\text{pyridine}$, (ii) $p\text{-ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2/\text{EtOH}$ and (iii) $\text{ClCO}_2\text{Et}/\text{pyridine}$.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were

recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 2000 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CD_3OD) on a Varian A 60D spectrometer with TMS as internal standard.

2,4-Dialkoxy-5-alkylbenzaldehydes were converted into the corresponding semicarbazones which were cyclised by oxidative cyclisation with bromine in glacial acetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate to give 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles¹.

Ethyl-N-[5-(2',4'-dimethoxy-5'-ethylphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]carbamate (2): To 2-amino-5-(2',4'-dimethoxy-5'-ethylphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (0.04 mol) in pyridine (160 ml) were added ethyl chloroformate (0.044 mol) and triethylamine (10 ml), and the mixture was refluxed for 1–2 h, then poured into dilute HCl (50%) and the carbamate thus formed was recrystallised from ethanol: 2a (50%), m.p. 197°; b (52%), 167–68°; c (61%), 210°; d (63%), 174°; e (56%), 191°; f (40%), 172–73°; g (54%), 185°; h (50%), 202°; i (59%), 162°; j (55%), 179–80°; k (52%), 181°; l (54%), 205°.

*N*¹-[5-(2',4'-Dimethoxy-5'-ethylphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl]-*N*³-(4-chlorophenyl)urea (3): An equimolar mixture of 2a and 4-chloroaniline in ethanol was refluxed for 20–22 h, then ethanol was removed and the residue washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol: 3a (64%), m.p. 182°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 (NH) and i 660 cm^{-1} (C=O); b (59%), 167°; c (63%), 175–76°; d (62%), 187°; e (64%), 192°; f (61%), 163–64°; g (57%), 202°; h (64%), 177°; i (61%), 195–96°; j (59%), 168°; k (60%), 206°; l (55%), 189°.

2-(2',4'-Dimethoxy-5'-ethylphenyl)-6-(4-chlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazolo[3,2-*a*]-*s*-triazine-5,7-diones (4): To a solution of 3a (0.01 mol) in pyridine (40 ml) was added ethyl chloroformate in an ice-bath. The mixture was then stirred at room temperature for 2–3 h, refluxed for 2 h, treated with 1*N* KOH (40 ml) and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol: 4a (58%), m.p. 162–63°; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 660 (C=O) and 700 cm^{-1} (C–Cl); δ (CDCl_3) 1.00 (3H, t, *J* 6.5 Hz, ArCH_2CH_3), 2.62 (2H, q, *J* 6.5 Hz, ArCH_2CH_3), 3.79 (6H, s, 2 × OCH_3), 7.5 (6H, m, ArH); b (60%), 170–71°; c (55%), 165–66°; d (57%), 161°; e (62%), 175–76°; f (59%), 160–61°; g (58%), 180°; h (58%), 175°; i (60%), 169–70°; j (62%), 184–85°; k (59%), 167°; l (61%), 177–78°. All the compounds (4a–l) gave satisfactory results for C, H and N.

The compounds (4a-1) were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activities against *Sarcina lutea*, *Candida albicans* and *Staphylococcus aureus* using agar diffusion method² at 1 mg ml⁻¹ concentration and exhibited a low degree of inhibition against all of them (10-15 mm zone of inhibition).

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